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Review of Methods for Exploratory Data Analysis for Copper Prices 1960-2020

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Abstract

This paper presents a statistical analysis of the historical data for global copper prices from the World Bank for the period from 1960 to 2025. This paper presents methods and results for several different approaches. The paper uses time-lag diagrams to show price transition periods as a feature of chaos theory established in other research. The paper also shows methods for using percentile rankings along different dimensions—for example, the years where the copper price increased the most. The paper also shows pathwise data analysis methods that use overlapping data samples to generate rankings about the data on a monthly basis, compared with an ensemble of values from all other paths in the dataset. For example, what did the all-time best five years in the copper markets look like based on the trailing-twelve-month price increase? The paper discusses how these methods can be used to make predictions and how the methods can be used for time series of other base metals, like zinc, or unrelated economic statistical time series.

Keywords: Statistics, Time Series, Methods, Copper, Mining, Finance, World Bank, Exploratory Data Analysis, 1960-2025, Global

JEL Codes:

A19 - Other	K23 - Regulated Industries
B59 - Other (120)	L2 - Firm Objectives, Organization,
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C02 - Mathematical Methods	L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products
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Review of Methods for Exploratory Data Analysis for Copper Prices 1960-2020

This paper presents a statistical analysis of the historical data for global copper prices from the World Bank for the period from 1960 to 2025. This paper presents methods and results for several different approaches. The paper uses time-lag diagrams to show price transition periods as a feature of chaos theory established in other research. The paper also shows methods for using percentile rankings along different dimensions—for example, the years where the copper price increased the most. The paper also shows pathwise data analysis methods that use overlapping data samples to generate rankings about the data on a monthly basis, compared with an ensemble of values from all other paths in the dataset. For example, what did the all-time best five years in the copper markets look like based on the trailing-twelve-month price increase? The paper discusses how these methods can be used to make predictions and how the methods can be used for time series of other base metals, like zinc, or unrelated economic statistical time series.

There is a rich literature on copper markets. For example, Duvhammar (2018) provides an analysis of the market microstructure for copper with theory and empirical work. Cortez, Coulton, and Sammut (2018) provide an example of research using methods from chaos theory in copper markets. The quote below is based on statistical methods from chaos theory applied to copper price history, which introduces the concept of a price transition period that has implications for the copper mining industry:

“We reveal that the annual copper price time series do not exhibit periodic behaviour and are not generated by a stochastic process. In addition, we observe the presence of a strange attractor describing an orbit running through a “stable” low-price state only interrupted by several years of price increases. We name these fluctuations “price transition periods,” which should be addressed as exceptional adjustment periods rather than cycles.”

(Cortez, Coulton, Sammut, 2018)

The first result in this article is to calculate the Hurst exponent as 0.88 for copper prices from 1960 to 2025. The method for calculating is described in (Mansukhani, 2012) for rescaled analysis. The value of the Hurst Exponent for copper price levels shows that it is a “persistent” time series where trends continue.

Table 1: Calculation of Hurst Exponent for Copper Prices 1960-2025

Slope		0.88
Log(N)	Log(Average R/S)	
	3.91	2.94
	4.61	3.80
	5.30	4.16

Price Levels and Differences

This paper starts with price levels. There are new all-time highs for price levels in 2025, which means a new value for the 100th percentile observation. This is a period of increased volatility, but how does it compare to other historical periods? For example, how does the trailing-twelve-month growth rate in 2025 compare to other periods? Figure 1 shows the 12-month price path for copper prices in 2025, which is the 58th percentile for all 12-month price paths based on results in this paper. Figures 2 and 3 show further information about the copper price levels from 1960 to 2025.

This paper also investigates price changes as introduced in Figures 4 and 5. There are several types of changes, such as monthly changes in raw data. Or the trailing twelve months (TTM), calculated as a compound growth rate. There are several examples where the TTM growth rate is 0.5, which means the copper price decreased 50% by month-month from the year prior. We also see TTM over 2.0, which means the price doubled from a year prior! The extreme values in TTM are a statistical feature that reflects the “persistence” of the copper price as predicted by the Hurst Exponent value greater than 0.5 as calculated in this paper above.

Figure 1: Copper Prices from 2021-2025 setting New All-Time-Highs

Figure 2: Copper Prices from 1960-2025 setting New All-Time-Highs

Figure 3: Partial Distribution for Copper Prices 1960-2025 Full Dataset

Figure 4: Comparing the Monthly Price Changes and Trailing Twelve Months Compound Price Change for 1960-2025 as Price Levels set New All-Time-Highs

Figure 5: Comparing Monthly Price Changes and the Trailing Twelve Months Compound Price

Histogram of Copper Price Changes (Monthly vs Trailing Twelve Months)

Pathwise Analysis of Copper Price Levels and Differences

This paper uses several types of pathwise methods. The pathwise analysis uses overlapping chunks of data with one-year or five-year data windows, sampled twice per year. These are examples of pathwise analysis methods that compare statistical features of ensembles of time series data, rather than individual values. For the 1-year data, the pathwise percentiles are calculated as follows: the value for each path is ranked against all others for each of the 12 monthly observations, then the percentile for each path is the average ranking over the monthly observations. The percentiles for the 5-year data windows are calculated in the same way. In this way, the pathwise percentile methods rank the different paths based on their rankings at each time step and across all time steps.

These methods help provide empirical ways to explore the idea of persistence in time series because the methods can be used to identify clusters. For example, do the worst periods in the copper markets have similar patterns for the decline in price? These methods can be used to identify the paths that are most extreme in one way or another. The following figures show the 1-year and 5-year paths for the largest percentiles, smallest percentiles, and median values.

Figure 6: Best Ensembles for 1-Year Long Paths

6 Paths with Largest Pathwise Percentiles

Figure 7: Worst Ensembles for 1-Year Long Paths

6 Paths with Lowest Pathwise Percentiles

Figure 8: Median Ensembles for 1-Year Long Paths

6 Paths with Median Pathwise Percentiles

Figure 9: Worst Ensembles for 5-Year Path Lengths

6 Paths with Lowest Pathwise Percentiles

Figure 10: Median Ensembles for 5-Year Path Lengths

6 Paths with Median Pathwise Percentiles

Figure 11: Best Ensembles for 5-Year Path Length

6 Paths with Largest Pathwise Percentiles

Figure 12: All 12-Month Price Paths for 1960-2002 Era

Figure 13: All 12-Month Price Paths for 2002-2025 Era

Figure 14: All 5-Year Price Paths for 1960-1990 Era

Figure 15: All 5-Year Price Paths for 2002-2025 Era

These pathwise methods can provide useful ways to understand current events. For example, the 5-year path that started on 2021M01 and ends on 2025M12 is the 59th percentile. However, the 1-year path that ends on 2025M12 is the 69th percentile. These results mean that the year 2025 had an unusually large price increase on a 1-year basis, but the 5-year window ending in 2025 was not unusual.

Percentile Rankings Methods and Results

This section provides a set of graphics that combine the pathwise percentiles and other data. The graphics use different dimensions of data, like price levels or changes. We start with the TTM price change calculated on a rolling basis to identify what years had the largest price increases, for example. This section also provides another view of the data based on the percentile ranking of all-time copper price levels, abstracted from the year of observation. This section also presents time lag plots for different eras to show examples of price transitions.

Figure 16: Ranking the TTM Price Changes and the corresponding year for each observation

Figure 17: Cumulative Distribution for Trailing Twelve-Month Price Change

Cumulative Frequency (%) of TTM Copper Price Change (%)
Copper Prices 1960-2025 World Bank

Figure 18: Percentile rankings for Copper Price Level, All-Time Data

Cumulative Percentile of Copper Price Levels, all-time

Figure 19: Cumulative Distribution for Copper Price Level, All-Time Data

Cumulative Percentile for Copper Price Levels

Figures 20 and 21 below show the time-lag plots for the price levels and the TTM price changes. The lag plots for the price levels show some variability in lagged values, as in Figure 20, but the way the TTM are calculated using a rolling average means that the lagged values have overlapping values, and the changes fall on a line, as in Figure 21. The lag plots for the price levels show some variability in lagged values, as in Figure 20.

Figures 22 and 23 calculate the time-lag plot with the same axes range of values for each era, showing how the copper price scale changed from 1960 to 2002 to 2002-2205. It is possible to separate time periods in different ways for further analysis, but these two data periods show stylized features. Both eras had similar lag plots; however, the later period was on a larger scale. These changes represent the price transition periods for copper price from chaos theory, as in (Cortez, Coulton, and Sammut, 2018).

Figure 20: Time Delay Plot for Copper Price Level, All-Time Data

Time Delay plot of Price (Lag t=1)

Figure 21: Time Delay Plot for Copper Price Trailing Twelve Month Changes, All-Time Data

Time Delay plot of TTM Price Change(Lag t=1)

Figure 22: Time Delay Plot for Copper Price Level, 2002-2025 Era

2002-2025 Time Lag Plot

Figure 23: Time Delay Plot for Copper Price Level, 1960-2002 Era

1960-2002 Time Lag Plot

Discussion

A key feature in the search for good empirical examples of data analysis is a relatively large number of observations on a time series basis. This paper has fewer than 1,000 monthly observations, which is a relatively small number for advanced statistical analysis. However, the data from 1960-20205 covers different eras of economic history that may be associated with statistical patterns that can be visualized using the methods in this paper.

Copper is a base metal, like zinc. It is possible to calculate the results presented in this paper for other data, like the price of zinc instead of copper. The methods can be used in the same way or changed for different metals. Also, additional methods can be used to compare the joint distribution of several time series, like copper and zinc together. Time lag plots can be used to show whether the different metals are going through similar patterns of price transition periods at the same time. The methods in this paper can also be used for unrelated economic time series data. These can be broadly defined data, such as global copper production, or specifically defined data, such as U.S. exports of copper scrap from the monthly Mineral Industry Survey report published by the United States Geological Survey (2025)

It may be possible to consider narrative descriptions of copper markets with these methods. For example, sentiment analysis of financial publications like the Wall Street Journal for the period 1960 to 2025 may reveal market attitudes towards the metal as it compares with statistical aspects of prices. Is there negative sentiment before prices start rising and positive sentiment when they start falling, or more complicated relationships between prices and sentiment? We can further include information about global statistics that measure things like political uncertainty or economic uncertainty. These different data may have surprising statistical relationships that help guide new theoretical understanding. Using more, better data may also improve the potential for simulation on a going-forward basis and prediction in live settings.

It may also be possible to use these statistical methods for the pathwise analysis to make predictions about the future based on current conditions, and there are various ways to select subsets of all the data to use for the prediction of future values based on theoretical assumptions. For example, we can draw at random from historical 12-month paths to predict the next 12 months. Or we can draw from a subset of paths that have some specific criteria, such as similar values for the prior six observations on a rolling basis. It is beyond the scope of this paper, but it may be helpful to use data for other commodity prices from the World Bank data set to represent exogenous changes in the global economy as a way to find analogues for historical time periods that represent good comparables for current conditions. Also possible to include global economic data to identify historical periods that provide useful comparisons to current conditions and enhance the predictive power of percentile ranking methods. It is possible to use these methods on a going-forward basis to test and compare them.

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